

SADC'S TRANSPORT INFRASTRUCTURE: ENHANCING THE AfCFTA'S PROSPECTS THROUGH REGIONAL ECONOMIC INTEGRATION

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Abstract

There is considerable significance, associated with the fact that the African Continental Free Trade Agreement (AfCFTA) has the potential to lift 68 million people out of moderate poverty. If fully implemented, the AfCFTA is estimated to increase regional income by 7 % by 2035. Operationalizing and implementing the African Continental Free Trade Area strategy, including regulating the regional economies' transport infrastructure, requires a great deal of work. It is the purpose of this article to examine how Regional Economic Communities (RECs), such as the Southern African Development Community (SADC), can contribute to the AfCFTA.

In comparison with other regional blocs, intra-SADC trade represents only 10 to 14 percent of member countries' total trade [1, 2]. Despite Southern African trade routes and infrastructure being among the best. In terms of infrastructure coverage, Southern African countries still lag behind the rest of the world, whether it's road and telecommunications technology (ICT), population density, or power generation. Whether at the national or regional level, these types of infrastructure weaknesses reinforce the infrastructure deficit and exacerbate unemployment, inequality and poverty in the region.

For the purposes of this article, a qualitative approach is being used to examine primary and secondary literature, including statistics, reports, and journal articles. According to the results of the study, the REC's infrastructure strategy will positively affect trade and, in turn, boost AfCFTA by improving trade among member states. To spawn structural transformation and create transnational growth corridors capable of driving economic growth and technological advancement, new transformative strategies are required.

Keywords: AfCFTA, Infrastructure, Intra-Africa Trade, regional economic communities, liberalisation, growth corridors, intra-regional trade, regional integration, Southern African Development Community (SADC).

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1. Introduction

On 21 March 2018, 44 members of regional economic communities from the African continent signed the AfCFTA in Kigali. Eritrea was the only state not to have signed the agreement as of July 2019 [3]. The AfCFTA was negotiated by African states, yet no trade partners have signed partnership agreements with the AfCFTA Group of African states, thus proving AfCFTA's potential to become not only the largest free trade agreement on the African continent, but also the largest free trade agreement in the world [4, 5].

AfCFTA was conceived by African leaders who saw the need for integration of the African market and viewed cooperation rather than unilateralism as the most effective way to intensify regional economic integration and global trade [6]. There is no doubt that Africa is open for business, given that there are a number of opportunities, such as the rapidly growing middle class, – most examples of rapid sustained economic growth occur alongside the construction and expansion of the middle class in developing countries [7, 8].

Given this, historically, the colonial powers and later competing superpowers and regional powers, generally did not encourage transport links, such as road links between their respective spheres except where absolutely necessary (i.e. trade), and in newly independent African states, border restrictions were often tightened rather than relaxed as a way of protecting internal trade, as a weapon in border disputes, and to increase the opportunities for official corruption [9–12].

Given this, trade infrastructure remains a cornerstone for the advancement of intraregional and extraregional trade for the African continent.

Furthermore, this also emphasizes the importance of economic integration on the African continent as well as the critical need to understand how world politics affects our everyday lives and how these issues can be addressed. Notably, the AfCFTA, which is meant to advance intra-regional and extraregional trade, cannot be successful and advance opportunities unless Africa's RECs are involved. Through these regional bodies, a greater amount of intraregional trade among African states could be enabled, which are lacking at present, while a more secure environment could be created [13].

Given this, South Africa has been hailed as the gateway into Africa, hence any country wanting to do business in Africa must consider the South Africa as a key strategic and business partner. Gateways, according to American geographer Saul Cohen [11], provide a link between the regional level and the global level of the world economy, serving as a conduit for ideas, people, and goods [14, 15]. Gateway countries take on a greater role within their respective regions, emerging as natural leaders. In view of South Africa's outsized role in international affairs across the African continent and beyond, it seems to fit this description. This is due to its human capital, infrastructure, and institutions have seemingly overcome this relative disadvantage in the past [16].

South Africa is one of the member states of the SADC regional bloc. In comparison with other regional blocs, intra-SADC trade represents only 10 to 14 percent of member countries' total trade [1, 2].

Despite Southern African trade routes and infrastructure being among the best. In terms of infrastructure coverage, Southern African countries still lag behind the rest of the world [15], whether it's road and telecommunications technology (ICT), population density, or power generation [17]. Whether at the national or regional level, these types of infrastructure weaknesses reinforce the infrastructure deficit and exacerbate unemployment, inequality and poverty in the region [17].

The Southern African Development Community (SADC) Regional Infrastructure Development Master Plan currently projects the following increases: By 2030, traffic for landlocked SADC countries will increase to 50 million tonnes, ramping to 148 million tonnes by 2040 – an 8.2 % annual growth rate; Port traffic will expand from 92 million tonnes to 500 million tonnes by 2027; Port expansion projects at Dar-es-Salaam will only sustain shipment traffic through 2020; OR Tambo International Airport in Johannesburg, South Africa, will add two million passengers a year by 2030 and three million a year by 2040; and Kenneth Kaunda International Airport in Lusaka, Zambia and N'djili International Airport in Kinshasa, Democratic Republic of the Congo, currently operate at 70 % of capacity, but expect traffic to expand well over 100 % of capacity by 2020 [18].

For the purposes of this article, a qualitative approach is being used to examine primary and secondary literature, including statistics, reports, and journal articles. According to the results of the study, the REC's infrastructure strategy will positively affect trade and, in turn, boost AfCFTA by improving trade among member states. To spawn structural transformation and create transnational growth corridors capable of driving economic growth and technological advancement, new transformative strategies are required.

To advance the SADC's transport infrastructure policy architecture, this study examines the potential for the region and its impacts on the AfCFTA. By drawing on SADC transport infrastructure integration key projects, this study aims to influence the advancement of the AfCFTA and address the challenges hindering transport integration. This case study emphasizes the importance of RECs, their trade and peace policies, and strategies of trade on the African continent through this case study. The purpose of this study is to propose a review of the SADC's trade policies to ensure greater political will and commitment from member states of regional blocks to implement and follow the trade infrastructure policies.

2. Materials and Methods

The study was qualitative in nature. There is a fair amount of research on the transport infrastructure of SADC. Due to the fact that many SADC trade routes are still colonial and the emerging

transport infrastructure is primarily financed by foreign governments or third parties, the reasons for a review over time. As a result, this study contributes to the limited knowledge about the status of SADC's trade infrastructure as well as its importance for the AfCFTA.

To answer the questions and hypotheses, data collection and documentation were the main components of the study. To begin with, an exploratory literature review was conducted, examining definitions, theories, viewpoints, principles, methods, and other research findings, as well as collecting newspaper articles from two prominent newspapers. In addition, secondary research was conducted using both primary and secondary sources. Primary internet data from the SADC secretariat and secondary journal articles that documented literature and research of the SADC transport infrastructure were the primary sources used. Books, internet sources, and documents that contained descriptive articles and commentaries were the secondary sources, used in this study. It is necessary to examine regional economic communities like SADC transport infrastructure in order to understand best practices within the region and identify gaps, associated to the RECs and their impact on the AfCFTA's, in order to put forward prescriptions. For these changes to take effect, the current model needs to be reviewed.

3. Results and discussion

Regional integration in Africa

As far as economic and labour growth is concerned, regional integration continues to be a powerful force to be reckoned with in order to ensure that labour markets are flourishing and that economies expand. Basically, regional integration promotes the sharing of public goods and infrastructure costs between states, enables them to decide policies cooperatively, and serves as an anchor for reforms. As well as serving as a building block for global integration, it has also proven to reap other non-economic benefits, such as contributing to a better quality of life for communities, ensuring the peace and security of those communities, and reaping other benefits that are not economically based.

Clearly, the new wave of regionalism plays a significant role in addressing the study's primary research question. According to Booth, Buzan, Nathan, Pins, Klare, Kaplan, and Tandon [19], security has evolved from its traditional focus on ensuring the stability of the state's military to becoming increasingly concerned with the welfare of the public. Historically, state security has been used to protect political interests for quite some time. As a result, it has become necessary for the SADC system to include a number of human threats, such as abuse of human rights, authoritarian regimes, and environmental threats, all of which are common to the SADC region.

There has been a second wave of regional cooperation in recent years, referred to as the new regionalism, which began in the 1980s, after the decline of integration theory and practice in the 1970s as a result of the decline of integration theory and practice. It can be argued, that this decline was caused both by the slowdown in West European integration as well as the failure of free trade agreements in Third World countries.

It is important to keep in mind, that there are four main types of regional economic integration. By integrating regionally, countries are able to bridge divisions that impede the flow of goods, services, capital, people, and ideas between countries. As part of regional integration, countries need to work together on a variety of issues, such as trade, investment, domestic regulation, transport, technology, and energy infrastructure, macroeconomic policy, and the provision of other common public goods (such as natural resources, security, and education).

An economic cooperation can be described in two ways in a free trade area: a free trade zone is one type of economic cooperation, while a customs union is another type of economic cooperation. It is similar to a free trade area in the sense that it provides economic cooperation through economic cooperation.

Regional integration can be interpreted along a number of notions. Ravenhill [20] points out that the commonality between these various notions is the premise that "armed conflicts is inconceivable among their member states." Ravenhill [20] aligns this view with the work, done by Nye [21] on the construction of "parts in parts", and sets out to categorise regions as economic or political constructions.

Zondi [22] claims that there is no agreement on the definition of regional integration, as territory is used to define the latter. Even though this is prevalent, continental terminology, such as the Lagos Plan of Action and the New Partnerships for Africa's Development (NEPAD), are also termed regional programmes. Furthermore, the term regional integration is also linked to countries with common characteristics, as well as shared political and economic initiatives. This ultimately seeks to secure common economic interests among the member states and explains the fact that in SADC, even turbulent states and geographically-distant states, such as the Democratic Republic of the Congo (DRC) and Madagascar, which cause insecurity within the region, still form part of the SADC bloc.

In essence, this new regionalism implies a change in the regional composition from relative heterogeneity to increased homogeneity, which is determined by a number of factors, of which culture, security, economic policy, and political regime are among the most important. In terms of its scope, nature, and multidimensionality, this new regionalism is comprehensive, multifaceted, and multidimensional.

Haas [23] characterises integration as a “process whereby political actors in several distinct national settings are persuaded to shift their loyalties, expectations and political activities towards a new centre.” Security cooperation requires states and regional bodies to focus on both the survival and development of their community. However, for this to occur effectively, there is a need for political will among member states as well as strong bonds within the community. These bonds will help them achieve the objectives of their affiliation. This is where institutions possess jurisdiction on pre-existing national states. The same would apply to a security community, in which political activities would be focused on security matters within the region.

There are a number of economic integration stages that one can decide to follow in order to achieve complete economic integration in the future: preferential trade areas, free trade areas, customs unions, common markets, economic unions, economic and monetary unions, and total economic integration.

Asante [22] characterises regional integration as “a process where two or more countries in a particular area voluntarily join together to pursue policies and objectives in a matter of general economic development or in a particular economic field of common interest to mutual advantage of all participating states.” In addition, Schneider [24] indicates that regional integration entails “common identity” institutions, which express the existence of and secure a unity effort within a region.

This collective security effort, which requires political will and commitment towards a common goal, was once part of the psyche of Southern African states' security collective. However, the same sense of urgency and collective effort is no longer evident. This has been demonstrated by the lack of unity of effort in decisions pursued. The latter may be due to the absence of an urgent goal, such as the desire for liberated African states. What is more, liberation struggles resulted simultaneously to regime changes, hegemonic behaviour, and military power increases. This confirms global inequalities, which have created clear winners and losers within the international security order.

Mbuede [25] suggest, regional integration is therefore categorised as having different stages and defining moments of collective cooperation. It is meant to focus predominantly on increased trade among members. Conversely, security cooperation is about creating common norms, institutional values, and structures, which promote peace and curtail security threats. Apart from economic integration, the end result of regional integration should be the promotion of the political union, which enables the unification of political institutions [26, 27]. What remains important in answering the main research question of this study is that the course of action in the integration process might not follow a pattern of accomplishment similar to that of other regional blocs – notably the European Union (EU). Furthermore, the formation of such regional trade grouping ultimately serves as a prerequisite for global trade liberalisation [28].

It is very interesting to note, that despite widespread economic crises and recessions that have taken place across most of the world over the last decade, Africa's economic growth and performance have been some of the best in the world [29]. The growth rate, however, has not led to a

significant and commensurate drop in poverty levels, nor has it resulted in a significant growth in employment opportunities, Mbuede [25].

For the SADC, the process of regional integration remains different to that of other regional blocs. This is due to the differing context, that is, the Southern African sub-regional grouping focuses on “development integration” and the three principles of the regional cooperation process, namely, political cooperation, functional cooperation, and market integration. As a result, the regional integration process has become complex and therefore difficult to analyse and measure.

Zondi [22] notes that old regionalism focused on decolonising African states in relation to the global economy and overcoming dependence on colonial powers. With regard to security, Thompson *et al.* [30] observe that the difference between “new security thinking” and “critical human security” is that the former includes military security threats. Booth [31], Vale [32], and Booth and Vale [33] have contributed to a better understanding of International Relations and security in the post-Cold War era. Bryant [34] postulates that, in the case of Southern Africa, security policy cannot be separated from development. This is further supported by Booth [31] who indicates that the “military, economic, political, societal and environmental aspects of insecurity [are] linked to development.”

It was during the period 1950-1970 that the old regionalism advanced into a “new regionalised world order” [35]. Ever since, new regionalism has evolved in content and context. Hettne and Soderbaum [36] note that old regionalism was characterised by the Cold War structure, whereas new regionalism is associated with how the globe has transformed.

Conversely, new regionalism emerged in the 1990s, a period, marked by the formation and proliferation of Regional Integration Arrangements (RIAs). Consequently, member states joined regional blocs and were expected to surrender their sovereignty. Whether this actually occurred remains open for exploration. It must be emphasised, that excluded members can form other trade blocs [37]. This has the potential of negatively impacting on regional security, creating trade war, and eradicating protectionism.

Zondi [24] suggests that the SADC’s evolution into a community required it to embrace new regionalism. Nonetheless, the SADC continued to maintain a similar set-up in its operations, and remained linked to structures and systems, aligned to old regionalism and state integration. The reason for this was that the old regionalism focused on the dependency theory, which related under-development in the South to exploitation and oppression by external actors and acknowledged that the international economy benefited some states. Hence, the solution to overcoming this was a new regionalism, which called for greater solidarity, pulling together economies of scale to overcome these external threats by creating self-reliance within the SADC member states. However, human security threats have become the new security hindrances in that they co-exist with states and regions.

Gunning [37] traces the origins of the first wave of regionalism in the SADC to the 1960s–1970s. This wave focused more on expanding the Southern African region. The second wave of regionalism occurred in the SADC region in the 1990s; it is directly linked to Article 14 of the SADC Treaty and is in accordance with the Abuja Treaty. The result has been a large number of RIAs – with multiple memberships. This led to confusion and a lack of synergy in the efforts of member states.

New regionalism, which is often referred to as a new wave of regionalism, can be characterised by various factors. The first is a new international division of power – from a bipolar Cold War structure to a multi-polar structure. The second is the purported decline of American hegemony. The third is the transformation of a political economy into a capitalist system, based on the European Union (EU), the North-American Free Trade Area (NAFTA), and the Asian-Pacific (ASEAN). The fourth is the end of the Westphalia nation-state system, the growth of the transnationalism, which led to political, social, and economic interaction among governments and actors. The fifth is the fact that the globalisation of trade, technology, finance, and production have led to a New International Division of Labour. The sixth is the fear of the multi-lateral trading order and the importance of both trade tariffs and barriers. The seventh factor is the end of “Third Worldism” and changes in the attitude of economies and political systems [36]

Soderbaum and Hettne [36] indicate that the “new wave of regionalism” became evident after the 1990s, due to an increase in relations between Africa and the West. Hence, it is characterised as multifaceted, multidimensional, globalisation, security, economics, political regimes, heterogeneity, and social dimensions. New regionalism allows for external opportunities, such as “trade, capital flows, technology, knowledge and manpower.

3. 1. Regional integration as a mechanism for advancing transport infrastructure

In order to determine the relevance of this region’s economic cooperation, it is important to analyze the regional integration mechanisms, implemented by the SADC, along with their successes and failures. Rugumamu [38], indicates that regional integration seeks to ensure both economic growth among member countries and within the region as a whole. As a result of this process, the member states will be given the opportunity to promote their economies, to enable a greater collaboration that will support the common interests of all the member states.

Regional integration is when a collective of states within a region undertake to promote trade, whilst safeguarding their interests. They may have rules, regulations, treaties, and agreements, which regulate their functioning, as is the case in The SADC’s Protocol on Transport, Communications and Meteorology. In addition to the supporting documents that are meant to make this aspiration a reality and include the (Nyirabu, 2004; Visser,2004)

- Final SADC Guidelines on Cross-Border Transport during COVID-19, adopted on 6 April 2020 – English
- Regional Infrastructure Development Master Plan Executive Summary 2012
- Regional Infrastructure Development Master Plan Transport Sector Plan 2012
- Regional Infrastructure Development Master Plan Meteorology Sector Plan 2012
- Protocol on Transport, Communications and Meteorology 1996
- SADC Regional Indicative Strategic Development Plan (RISDP) 2020–2030
- SADC Regional Indicative Strategic Development Plan (RISDP) Summary – English
- SADC Vision 2050

As has been highlighted, regional integration is a global practice, which requires various components to work together with organisations at national and regional levels. Furthermore, collective transport infrastructure development – together with good governance, civil participation, and the institutionalisation of democracy can ensure increased trade, fostering strong economies and sustained peace and stability within a region. This also fosters integration with other regions [38], such as the European Union (EU), China and the United States of America (USA).

Partnerships and collaboration remains important objectives for the economic advancement of regional economic communities and their cooperation [39, 40].

The scramble for Africa’s resources both under colonialism and in the decolonisation periods cast obscurity, cynicism, and doubt over the ability of international and regional organisations to deal with advancing Africa’s ability to become industrialised economies that determine their own agenda when it comes to transport infrastructure, economic development and instituting thriving economies [41]. The end of the Cold War signaled the search for a more effective and efficient regional economic architecture structurally and systematically. This is why the notions of infrastructural development that exist in one continent or sub-region vary in comparison to others [42, 43].

In this study, it is argued, that there is a need for increased infrastructure development within Africa – through the use of collaborative transport infrastructure between African nation states [44, 45]. As an industrializing community, SADC is in need of a normative and practical framework to manage Africa’s infrastructure development agenda.

Lieberman [46] advises states to proceed with caution in the integration process. This is due to a lack of confidence in the process’s ability to unfold fully. However, the SADC might be the exception, because its mission is premised on ‘regional cooperation’. It must be noted, that the issues of regional cooperation and transport infrastructure are not new concepts to the SADC region.

In this regard, it should be noted, that the transport infrastructure in Southern Africa is significantly more established than other sectors of infrastructure, and that it had advanced during the period of postliberation in the region’s hegemon, South Africa. Currently, most SADC Member

States maintain dedicated road agencies, and extensive improvements have been made to regional railways and air transport to eliminate colonial trade routes and promote emerging trade routes within SADC. Given this Moyo [47] suggest that the decolonising of borders and the management of borders within the region require greater review, and will ultimately impact on deepening regional economic integration.

Fig. 1 illustrates, in SADC, there have been major developments along three primary corridors: the North-South Corridor in South Africa, the Maputo Corridor in Mozambique, and the Dar-es-Salaam Corridor in Tanzania. Furthermore, Durban is considered the biggest port in Africa and to be the most important port gateway in SADC, along with Cape Town, Port Elizabeth, Walvis Bay, Maputo, Lobito, and Dar es Salaam. Additionally, a multi-country corridor connecting South Africa to Zambia, the Democratic Republic of the Congo (DRC), Botswana, Malawi, and other countries, the North-South Africa Corridor is one of the largest corridors in Africa.

Fig. 1. SADC regional trade corridors

3. 2. The SADC and regional transport infrastructure

It is important to note that Southern Africa has a better infrastructure than other parts of the continent when it comes to infrastructure in terms of its development. The Seychelles, one of the SADC states, has some of the best infrastructure on the continent, with the highest level of development, in accordance with the Africa Infrastructure Development Index [48]. A recent survey of the Human Development Index World Population Review [49] (2023) indicates that Mauritius, another SADC member state, is the only African country, whose human development rating is high. Mauritius is the most developed country on the continent. There are also other member states of the SADC that have high human development indices, such as Seychelles and South Africa. South Africa has maintained its position as one of the most technologically advanced nations in the continent. South Africa is ranked 61 out of 132 countries that are featured in the 2021 Global Innovation Index (GII) among the 132 countries that are included in the study, making it the world's 61st most innovative country. As well as that, a Knight Frank report, titled Africa Horizons Report 2021/22, ranked Nairobi as the best city in Africa. There is no doubt that a number of SADC cities, such as

Cape Town and Johannesburg, are among the most developed in the world, making them economically important not only to Africa but to the world as a whole. South Africa's economy is one of the most industrialized, technically advanced, and diversified economies in Africa as a whole, being the third largest economy in the continent. While SADC states are recognized for their excellent infrastructure, they still fall behind in almost every measure of infrastructure coverage, whether it is the density of roads, the density of ICTs, or the generation of electricity [50].

In a statement, made by Wendworth and Cloete [17], Southern African countries are lagging behind the rest of the world in almost all areas of infrastructure provision. Especially true is this when it comes to the second pillar of the SADC Vision 2050, which addresses the issue of infrastructure development in order to facilitate the integration of the region within the framework of regional integration. A pre-COVID-19 assessment of the state of the infrastructure in Southern Africa, conducted by the Southern African Research and Documentation Centre, has found that reality is at odds with the vision, outlined in this report, despite this. At several stages of the preparation cycle, there has been a significant amount of stagnation that has resulted in the development of infrastructure not progressing from preparation to financial closure to implementation, which has resulted in a high level of stagnation that has been observed throughout the preparation cycle.

There are many institutional weaknesses in the region that are contributing to the widening of the infrastructure gap as well as the acceleration of unemployment, inequality and poverty by increasing the gap between the secretariat and the country. At either the national or secretariat level, weak points can occur that affect the country or secretariat as a whole.

Furthermore there are a number of fragile states that are only just starting out on their road to recovery, and this remains one of the main concerns for the AfCFTA. In order to effectively tackle these military and human security threats, the African continent and its regional economies will need to align their regional integration strategies and the TA architecture to be able to deal with the persistent nature of these insecurities. Vogel, 2022, and Humphreys, 2003 argue that peace processes ignore the role of free trade and industry in conflict resolution, even though these issues are often at the centre of violent conflicts between different groups. In the opinion of MacDonald [51], free trade contributes more to peace than any other form of trade. A further benefit of this is that it removes one of the major platforms for supporting wars and reduces the power of free trade interests when it comes to limiting foreign policy aggression, which is most often used as a way to build up a state's military infrastructure.

In addition to preventing the construction of roads, wars and conflicts have led to the destruction of roads and river crossings, have hindered maintenance and have often resulted in the closure of vital links as well. There are several SADC countries, which are in the process of rebuilding after wars, such as the Democratic Republic of the Congo, Mozambique and Angola. As a consequence of the civil war in the Democratic Republic of the Congo, the road infrastructure in that country has been pushed back decades, and the primary route between East and West Africa has been cut off. Additionally, in the countries that remain subject to war, road travel has been restricted over the past few years due to security concerns.

From a continental perspective, the trans-African highways have been a major consideration, aimed at interconnecting the African continents transport infrastructure. Using existing national highways as much as possible, the aim of the development agencies is to identify priorities in relation to trade, to plan the highways, and to seek financing for the construction of missing links and bridges, the paving of sections of earth and gravel roads, and the rehabilitation of deteriorated paved sections.

However the trans-African highways can only develop in times of peace and stability. As opposed to war, lawlessness and instability impedes progress in the development of the Highway, even though practical routes through other states remain considerations [52]. In order to make this article more understandable, it has been divided into four sections. In the first section of the article, background information on regional integration is provided and the main political calculus for the advancement of transport infrastructure in the region is discussed, emphasizing the larger strategic factors, associated with Africa's desire for deeper integration. This study discusses the SADC transport infrastructure and its impact on the AfCFTA in the second section. In the third section of

the study, it discusses the SADC's transport infrastructure, highlighting both its successes and its challenges. A conclusion is reached in the final section of the study.

3. 3. The SADC transport infrastructure impacting the advancement of the AfCFTA

There has been an integration agenda, established by the SADC since March 2004. The SADC plan called for a SADC customs union to be formed by 2010, a common market pact to be reached by 2012, a monetary union to be established by 2016, and a single common currency to be minted by 2018 [53, 54]. All of these plans have not yet been achieved and as argued by some scholars remain the key hindrances towards SADC's advances in regional economic integration [55].

In order to achieve SADC Infrastructure Vision 2027, six pillars of the SADC Regional Infrastructure Development Programme [18] are required to be met. These pillars are energy, transport, information and communication technologies (ICT), meteorology, trans-boundary water resources and tourism (trans-frontier conservation areas). The transportation infrastructure encompasses both fixed installations, such as roads, railways, airways, waterways, canals, and pipelines, as well as terminals, such as airports, railway stations, bus stations, warehouses, trucking terminals, fuelling stations, and seaports (including fuelling docks and fuel stations) [18].

The transportation infrastructure in Southern Africa has been in existence for a longer period of time than other sectors of the infrastructure. The majority of SADC's member states maintain dedicated roads agencies at present, while substantial improvements are being made to regional railways and the air transportation system in the region. It is the responsibility of Mozambique to maintain the transport infrastructure within the SADC [17].

As a developing region, Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) has a relatively low number of transport public-private partnerships (PPP), and it has a high number of failed projects, including the Lekki toll road concession in Nigeria, the N4 toll road in South Africa and Mozambique, and the Port of Maputo (Mozambique), which all required much more proficient implementation. It was suggested in a study by Osei-Kyei and Chan [56], that better implementation in collaboration with greater 'stakeholder management, transparent and competitive tendering process, high participation of local investors, stable macro-economic conditions and strong government commitment and regulatory framework,' were needed for success [56].

Habiyaremye [57] contends that some of the infrastructure projects impacting SADC's transport infrastructure can be attributed to China's Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) and infrastructure developments, such as the Benguela and TAZARA lines. Angola, Congo ("DRC"), Tanzania and Zambia are endowed with the richest natural resources, and the Benguela and TAZARA rail lines would become the backbone of the transport infrastructure through these areas. The strategic concept and design of the SADC Development Corridors are similar to the China Belt and Road Initiative ("BRI"). Through the TAZARA Corridor, the BRI could be linked to four strategic SADC Development Corridors. A critical aspect of the SADC Development Corridor and SDI socio-economic transformation model is the synchronization of infrastructure investments for the provision of economic services and the exploitation of natural resources, which are linked to industry and logistics platforms.

The holistic development model is intended to achieve comprehensive socio-economic transformation by promoting regional trade within SADC and increasing participation in international trade in value-added products through multimodal transport terminals in related Development Corridors and SDIs. In this regard, railway transport connectivity is crucial to providing the necessary carrying capacity to enable the movement of large quantities of raw materials from primary production centers to industrial platforms and ultimately deliver intermediates and finished products to respective markets [58].

Table 1 illustrates, key SADC transport infrastructure integration projects. The transport sector in Southern Africa has a greater level of established infrastructure than other sectors. Currently, most SADC Member States have dedicated road agencies, while major improvements are being made to regional rail and air transportation in most SADC countries.

Table 1
Infrastructural Development in Support of Regional Integration

Infra-structure	Previous development (15–20 years)	Plans for development	Emerging projects
1	2	3	4
Road and road transport	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – As assessed from 2001, the road infrastructure in Southern Africa is comparatively strong. – The road standards in Botswana, Lesotho, and Namibia were particularly good. – Approximately two-thirds of the road network in South Africa and Zimbabwe were and are in good condition. – Angola and Mozambique have neglected road maintenance, with 90 % of their roads considered fair to poor. – Currently, many traffic routes are in poor condition and have noticeable defects. Angola's rail network ranks 85th in the world with 0.08 meters per capita. There are 2,852 kilometers of rail network in total [59] – Mozambique had undertaken a major road rehabilitation programme. – In some key locations, there are still missing road links, making road transport difficult. Angola and the Democratic Republic of the Congo have the most missing links due to their large extractive industries that rely heavily on roads for trade. – There is a need to build new roads in these two Member States as well as repair damage, caused by conflict and neglect. – The cost of road maintenance remains a concern for the entire region. Despite the fact that Member States recognize the importance of a functional, integrated road network, funds are often diverted into other areas. The road network has also received substantial funding previously, but it has been inefficiently managed by governments in many Member States. Public-private partnerships and user-pays principles are currently being explored as alternatives to traditional top-down approaches to funding repairs and construction. – Southern Africa's railway system faces substantial challenges. – Since deregulation of road transport, traffic volume rapidly increased. – Since railways don't have fixed operating costs, a decline in traffic forced them to operate at a loss, with any income going toward salaries and fuel instead of maintenance and upkeep. Less investment in the rail system due to declining traffic and deteriorating infrastructure led to unsustainable rail networks. – In order to become sustainable, additional capacity requirements can be met through increased freight loads, though this increase has yet to occur due to the unreliability and cost inefficiency of the current rail network in comparison with road transport. – As the African Union promotes, new rail lines have been installed and expensive upgrades implemented, such as converting to European Standard Gauge rails. – Rail companies, however, would rather revive existing infrastructure, which is often promoted by governments. – Railway lines are beneficial under certain scenarios, but only when they are linked to productive industries, like the Moatize coal line in Mozambique. – The majority of rail infrastructure can be upgraded minimally and is simply underutilized. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> While the South African road network has sufficient capacity, projections indicate that it will need to be expanded by 2027. Due to heavy overloading and infrequent maintenance, the Regional Trunk Road Network requires rehabilitation. SADC's Regional Infrastructure Development Master Plan for 2012 outlines 72 road infrastructure and transport projects for the next 25 years, mostly along the North-South Corridor, Maputo Corridor, and Dar-es-Salaam Corridor. It is anticipated, that the following road projects will be operational by 2027: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Dar-es-Salaam – Chalinze toll road – Kazungula bridge – Nata – Kazungula road upgrading – Beitbridge – Chirundu road upgrading – Tete toll bridge – Western Corridor road in Zambia – The development of an intraregional road asset management system. By establishing additional road networks, landlocked Member States will be able to connect with major population and economic centers in a cost-effective manner. The Association of Southern African National Roads Agencies oversees these projects. The SADC region was provided with a commonly defined, integrated, and numerable regional road network in 2007 after commissioning a study of the Regional Trunk Road Network that included the Democratic Republic of the Congo; the study has influenced future network planning in the SADC region. 	<p>The Kazungula Bridge has been opened and a one-stop border post has been established</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – A US\$259 million Kazungula Bridge and One Stop Border Post have been commissioned, paving the way for enhanced SADC integration and development
Railways	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Southern Africa's railway system faces substantial challenges. – Since deregulation of road transport, traffic volume rapidly increased. – Since railways don't have fixed operating costs, a decline in traffic forced them to operate at a loss, with any income going toward salaries and fuel instead of maintenance and upkeep. Less investment in the rail system due to declining traffic and deteriorating infrastructure led to unsustainable rail networks. – In order to become sustainable, additional capacity requirements can be met through increased freight loads, though this increase has yet to occur due to the unreliability and cost inefficiency of the current rail network in comparison with road transport. – As the African Union promotes, new rail lines have been installed and expensive upgrades implemented, such as converting to European Standard Gauge rails. – Rail companies, however, would rather revive existing infrastructure, which is often promoted by governments. – Railway lines are beneficial under certain scenarios, but only when they are linked to productive industries, like the Moatize coal line in Mozambique. – The majority of rail infrastructure can be upgraded minimally and is simply underutilized. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The railway sector faces a number of challenges, but the region remains committed to revitalising it, handling several proposals for new projects. The SADC region has 31 rail projects under consideration as outlined in the 2012 Regional Infrastructure Development Master Plan. Although this interest is not uncommon, a properly implemented rail network is more cost-effective and fuel-efficient than road transport. Rail freight volumes must increase significantly for these projects to be financially viable. Public-private partnerships can mitigate financial risk by supporting many of the projects currently under development. In the short- to medium-term, the following projects are anticipated: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Chingola (Zambia) – Solwezi Railway Extension – Botswana – Lephale Railway – Moatize, (Mozambique) – Nacala Railway – Sena (Mozambique) – Railway Upgrading – Beira (Mozambique) – Machipanda Line Upgrading With these projects currently under development, the SADC region has the opportunity to develop rail infrastructure, while also fostering economic development. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> –

Continuation of Table 1

1	2	3	4
Private sector	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Development of policy guidelines on Public-Private sector Partnerships – Initiation of an institutionalised public-private dialogue – Incorporation of Private Sector representatives in SADC National Committees – Establishment of a Private Sector engagement unit in the SADC Secretariat – Inception of regional competitiveness and business climate surveys in the SADC region – Development of SADC a biannual business forum – Facilitation of a regional Private Sector organisation 	<p>Private sector achievements</p> <p>The private sector has been integrated into SADC decision-making forums in a number of ways to date. Several SADC Secretariat Directorates have established consultative mechanisms with the private sector on a variety of topics, including infrastructure development, food security, customs, and mining, with the support of various committees, even though SADC does not currently have a specific policy instrument to guide the development of public-private partnerships.</p> <p>In addition, the SADC Secretariat has negotiated Memorandums of Understanding (MOUs) with various regional business organizations, including the Association of SADC Chambers of Commerce and Industry (ASCCI) and the SADC Business Forum.</p> <p>As part of these initiatives, the SADC Development Finance Resource Centre (DFRC) has created a practitioner network on Public-Private-Partnerships (PPPs). In addition, SADC leveraged the global attention, generated by the 2010 FIFA World Cup in South Africa to promote sustainable investment opportunities and cooperation in the region.</p>	<p>Projects Underway</p> <p>64 maritime and inland waterway transport projects are currently being developed by Member States to meet these challenges. These projects concentrate on two centres: Dar-es-Salaam, Tanzania, and Walvis Bay, Namibia.</p> <p>Dar-es-Salaam anticipates a number of port infrastructure projects through 2027, including the expansion of existing ports and the construction of new ports at Mwambani Bay and Mbegani near Bagamoyo. Walvis Bay – one of only two deep-water ports in the region – will see its berths, container terminals, maintenance quays, and marinas expanded over the next 25 years. The ports of Nacala, Beira, and Maputo in Mozambique; Luanda in Angola; and Durban in South Africa are also undergoing major development.</p> <p>This development is largely the result of private sector involvement, which has been especially successful at implementing infrastructure that facilitates industrial development. Due to their connections to copper mines in Zambia and the Moatize coal mine in Mozambique, Dar-es-Salaam and Beira ports have greatly benefited from private sector investment. State bodies provided infrastructure for private enterprises to operate in these cases. Due to the success of these public-private partnerships, SADC is seeking similar partnerships to develop maritime and inland waterway transportation throughout the region.</p>

Continuation of Table 1

1	2	3	4
	<p>Current Challenges</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – SADC’s aquatic transport system is more developed than elsewhere in Africa, but still lags behind international standards. – Most countries have acceded to the Status of Convention of the International Maritime Organization, but lack the technical capacity to maintain these standards. 		
Maritime, Ports & Inland Waterways	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Due to poor integration with other modes of transport and slow clearance by regulators, most ports in the region operate near capacity. – Although many Member States have committed to expanding their port infrastructure, these expansions aren’t expected to meet the increased demand by 2020. – Aquatic transport in Southern Africa faces the following challenges, according to the Regional Infrastructure Development Master Plan released in 2012: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Road transport vehicles impede efficient operations in port areas. – Many ports aren’t able to handle materials correctly, regardless of their apparent capacity. – Ineffective customs procedures delay freight for up to two months, hindering supply chains. – Ports are usually located near densely populated industrial zones that restrict expansion – Railways still use obsolete break-bulk rail systems; access roads cross congested business, industrial, and residential areas, causing delays. – Ports have insufficient berths and drafts - Demand for berths is approaching or exceeding capacity. 		
	<p>Current Status</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – For the SADC region, the OR Tambo International airport in Ekurhuleni, South Africa, near Johannesburg, is the central hub for air traffic in Southern Africa. – Africa’s largest airport handles 28 million passengers annually, serving traffic from most countries on a daily basis, including through-traffic between capitals of SADC member states. – Johannesburg will accommodate an increase of two million passengers a year by 2030, increasing to three million passengers by 2040 as air traffic expands in the region. – Apart from minor scheduling and maintenance issues, most airports in the region are operating adequately. – Nevertheless, many of these airports are expected to exceed their capacity as traffic increases through stronger regional and global integration. – By 2020, the Kenneth Kaunda International Airport in Zambia and the N’djili International Airport in the Democratic Republic of the Congo will operate at over 100 % capacity. 		
	<p>Regulatory Challenges</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – International standards, conventions, and recommended practices must be strictly adhered to in air transport. – The SADC adheres to the International Civil Aviation Organization’s Standards and Recommended Practices, but domestic airlines may follow other standards. – There is no regional governing body and no unified policy or strategic framework specific to civil aviation in the region, even though there are many industry associations in Southern Africa, Airports Council International, and Civil Air Navigation Service Organisation. – In line with the International Civil Aviation Organization, the African Civil Aviation Commission promotes harmonised aviation policies. – SADC’s Regional Infrastructure Development Master Plan urges for the establishment of a regional coordinating body to oversee policy and implementation of a concerted civil aviation strategy. In response to this need, SADC initiated the Cooperative Development of Operational Safety and Continuing Airworthiness Program in 2008. – A forerunner to a permanent organisation overseeing air transport in the region, this program assists Member States in harmonising their national civil aviation regulations. – Since its inception, this program has made little progress. 		
Air and aviation	<p>Economic Challenges</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – In addition to requiring regional policy regulation, integrating SADC’s air transport industry also requires less economic regulation. – Aviation is a highly commercial enterprise that serves the region’s interests best when operated commercially. – Airlines and other aviation infrastructure within Member States are heavily regulated, often state-owned, and do not consider commercial interests, resulting in an economically unsustainable system of domestic travel. – In 1999, the African Union developed the Yamoussoukro Decision, recognizing the benefits of liberalising air transport markets. – African nations are urged to liberalise their air transport markets. – SADC promotes economic deregulation of the airline industry as well. – Members states’ concerns about competition undermining national carriers have slowed progress on liberalisation at a national level 	<p>Current Projects</p> <p>In addition to enhancing safety equipment and terminal facilities throughout the region, SADC Member States are upgrading their national air transport infrastructure in the following ways: Gaborone, Maun, Kasane, and Francistown airports are receiving significant investments for modernization in order to position Botswana as a regional hub for air passengers; The Ivato International Airport in Antananarivo is currently being upgraded; Maputo International Airport, the country’s most important airport, is modernizing, with new passenger and cargo terminals; The airports in Namibia are currently being upgraded; By investing in a Civil Aviation Training Centre, Tanzania aims to position itself as a hub for aviation education. Additionally, Dar-es-Salaam is planning to develop and expand its air transport facilities.</p>	

Source: SADC.Int [18]

3. 4. Issues with regional projects in SADC

Intractable challenges for regional projects are created by political interference, even at the highest level. The motivation for regional cooperation and connectivity is often driven by sovereign- and self-interest. Kazungula Bridge Project, for instance, is a multi-national infrastructure improvement programme on the North–South Corridor that includes a bridge over the Zambezi River. It replaces the existing ferry between Botswana and Zambia and provides a one-stop border facility, funded by Japan International Cooperation Agency, regional governments, and the EU-Africa Infrastructure Trust Fund. Since former President Robert Mugabe refused to allow the bridge to cross any part of Zimbabwe, the bridge incorporated Namibian territory and avoided Zimbabwe.

President Emmerson Mnangagwa's late involvement in the project can be seen as a regional integration achievement at the highest level. Regional cooperation is especially needed in a global crisis, as relationships with global powers are re-established.

It is not always the case, that external investors in regional infrastructure support intra-African cooperation, such as investors' motivations. Concessional infrastructure projects in regional African countries are often ambivalent – or accompanied by conditions, imposed by bilateral or multilateral partners. There have been negative experiences with foreign-built infrastructure in SADC. Historically, European powers supported infrastructure, designed to access Africa's raw materials.

A similar accusation has been levelled against China. Angola and Mozambique consistently complain about the quality of road infrastructure in Chinese-built infrastructure projects in Botswana between 2009 and 2015.

Limitations of the study. A desk study was conducted. Due to travel restrictions, any additional documentation that might be available at the REC was not included in this study. Visits to the SADC secretariat might have helped in identifying the current situation more clearly. In future studies, more recent audit reports or documents can be incorporated into this study to improve it.

The prospects for further research. As a result of this study, future research could explore how major transport infrastructure projects in different regions, such as major ports or corridors, will affect the AfCFTA's specific objectives and move Africa closer to becoming the world's largest free trade area. Comparative studies of the ramifications of 4IR could be conducted on the Djibouti-Addis Ababa Corridor on the eastern tip of Africa, which is home to the most technologically advanced container terminal on the continent. This is in comparison to the Port of Durban, one of the largest and busiest shipping terminals in sub-Saharan Africa, one of the traditional ports. Weighing colonial transport infrastructure against emerging transportation infrastructure.

Reviewing the RECs and their transport infrastructure framework could also strengthen the capabilities of the AfCFTA to increase intraregional trade within the continent.

4. Conclusion

This article discusses and analyzes SADC's transport infrastructure and its importance to the AfCFTA. Additionally, the role of regional economic integration in promoting increased trade, within the region was examined. Study findings indicate that AfCFTA's strategy affects the peace and security of member countries significantly. Without the involvement of Africa's RECs, AfCFTA cannot succeed and advance opportunities. These regional bodies can facilitate greater trade between African states, as well as create more industrialized states that will impact economies of scale. Compared to other emerging markets and free trade agreements, Africa can learn many lessons from Southern Africa.

Though the AfCFTA is still in its infancy, emerging economies, such as South Africa, a hegemon in the SADC region, play a significant role in the region's economic growth and peace. To further advance intraregional and extraregional trade, SADC needs to explore the possibility of prioritising regional transport projects. RECs would also be an important building block for the advancement of trade among African states, whose natural resources can be converted into finished products, thus further developing African economies. Additionally, there are many opportunities for intraregional trade. As a result, the AfCFTA can become the largest trade agreement in the world.

Despite this, Africa faces several challenges, such as a lack of essential infrastructure, an overreliance on third-party funding for infrastructure projects, and dependence on colonial trade routes as opposed to advancing the emergence of new trade routes.

With its geostrategic advantages and potential for economic integration, Africa will benefit from deeper integration and collaboration between the AfCFTA, the AU, and RECs when considering transport infrastructure. The AfCFTA will enhance Africa's economic position within the global economy if it meets its set goals. Therefore, the AfCFTA could set Africa on a trajectory that surpasses many other infrastructure development agreements.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest in relation to this paper, as well as the published research results, including the financial aspects of conducting the research, obtaining and using its results, as well as any non-financial personal relationships.

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Manuscript has no associated data

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